

Statistical reports and data analytics with distributed computing

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Project Specification

This project involves the following:

1. Data Analytics as a Service - Providing a way for users to write their own Data Analytics algorithms in R through the use of Jupyter. This will allow them to easily run and share their code, data and results.
2. Scale out data analytics algorithm using Docker - Parallelizing the algorithm across a cluster on Openstack by dividing the task over multiple nodes to execution time.

Once completed, this project will provide users with the necessary tools and infrastructure to be able to perform Data Analytics themselves on their data as well as view their results in a straightforward manner.

Figure 1:

1. The user writes a script in R and it is run on the master.
2. The master divides the task across the slaves.
3. Upon completion the results are displayed in the browser.

Abstract

The control systems needed to run the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), its injector accelerators and their infrastructure generate massive amounts of data. This data can be used to optimize the control systems, and provide meaningful information to the machines operators and experts. At present, algorithms perform Data Analytics on over 3000 signals each day, and this number is only increasing. Performing such a large amount of computations is time consuming, especially when run on a single machine. Therefore it is through this project that we aim to search for a means of parallelizing the execution of such algorithms. The proposed solution makes use of Docker which allows for straightforward scalability. Results show that scaling up the system does indeed decrease the execution time required.

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1 Introduction

1.1 What is Data Analytics as a Service?

Data analytics involves **performing an algorithmic process on the data provided in order to gain some insight**, such as searching for meaningful correlations across multiple data sets. It focuses on reaching conclusions based solely on the researchers' current knowledge. It is distinguished from data analysis and data mining as defined below:

- Data Analysis - The process of scanning through all the data in order to acquire information on it.
- Data Mining - The process of searching through data sets to identify undiscovered patterns and creating hidden relationships.

Data analytics helps organisations to better understand the information contained within the data as well as aids in identifying the most important data for current and future business decisions [1,2].

Data Analytics as a Service involves providing the necessary tools and infrastructure to make it possible for users to perform analytics on data themselves. From a functional perspective, Data Analytics as a Service provides the end-to-end capabilities of an analytical solution, from data acquisition to end-user visualization, reporting and interaction. It extends the typical approach with innovative concepts, such as; Analytical Apps and a related Analytical Appstore. Moreover, the platform also supports the needs of different users who interact with it [3].

1.2 Project Aim

The aim of this project is to explore, investigate and implement an approach for parallelizing the execution of algorithms in R. The objective is to accomplish this by:

1. Setting up Docker containers in order to be able to run the algorithm.
2. Setting up a cluster of nodes to work with the Docker containers.
3. Executing an algorithm across a number of nodes and containers.
4. Evaluating the feasibility and scalability of such an approach.

This will allow for any R algorithm to be split across various nodes with the aim of decreasing the amount of execution time required.

1.3 Motivation

Nowadays large companies face the problem of handling big data sources. Although combining Big Data and the Cloud makes it possible to introduce advanced analytic capabilities for such data, the problem is that companies are interested in the data itself, not the technology used to process it. Companies don't need the deployment of complex Big Data infrastructure, they need access to services which are able to provide advanced Data Analytics on their current and future data. Providing this service in a flexible and scalable format is the main purpose of Data Analytics as a Service.

1.4 Approach

The problem of providing Data Analytics as a Service in a scalable format is tackled through the use of Docker. Docker containers may be run on a cluster such that the work is split across these containers which are spread across multiple nodes. This way, if a specific algorithm requires a higher level of scalability, more containers may easily be started and assigned work. Moreover, if new nodes are added to the cluster, containers may just as easily be started on them.

2 Docker

2.1 Overview

Docker is an open platform which allows developers and system administrators to build, ship and run distributed applications inside containers, so that they may be run across various systems and machines. It offers a new way to run and deploy software applications through high-level tools and Linux kernel features.

This was made possible through the use of LXC (Linux Containers) based environments for creating Docker containers. Linux containers run in the same operating system as its host, allowing it to share most of its resources. Docker containers are created from Docker images which are built by manually executing commands or automatically using Dockerfiles [4].

2.2 Docker Containers and Images

When using Docker, whether on a local machine or a server in the cloud, all applications are run in containers. Docker containers are isolated and secure application platforms which store complete file systems which meet all the requirements to run a piece of software, such as: code, system tools and system libraries. This ensures that the software will always run the same irrespective of the environment used for execution [5].

The simplest way to start a container is by using the command:

```
$ docker run [OPTIONS] IMAGE [COMMAND] [ARGUMENT]
```

Upon receiving this command, Docker will create a new container based on the specified image, feed it the command and starts its execution. To run a container from an image Docker adds a read-write layer on top of the image, by using a Union File System, in which the application is able to run [6].

It is possible to follow a running container's logs by using the command:

```
$ docker logs [OPTIONS] IMAGE
```

Docker also provides the possibility to enter a running container to view its status and contents by using the following command:

```
$ docker exec [OPTIONS] IMAGE bash
```

Docker containers are launched using read-only Docker images whereby these images are saved states of containers. Images inform Docker what the container consists of, what process to run upon launching the container, as well as other configuration data. A container's state may be saved to an image such that the state may be re-used to create more complex containers or to run the same state on multiple machines.

Docker provides a straightforward way to build new images, update existing images and download ready-made images from the DockerHub. Each image is made up of layers which are combined into a single image using the union file system. Union file systems allow files and directories coming from separate file systems to be transparently overlaid, forming a single coherent file system. It is because of these layers that Docker is lightweight. When a change is made to a Docker image, a new layer is built rather than replacing the entire image and rebuilding from scratch. This also facilitates the distribution of images as only the updates need to be distributed [7].

Figure 2:

- A Docker image is situated directly on the kernel.
- Each instruction creates a new layer in the image.
- A Docker container is run based on a specified image.
- Each Docker container is isolated [8].

2.3 Dockerfiles

Dockerfiles store the instructions used to build an image whereby each instruction is run independently, creating a new layer each time. A Dockerfile is simply a text document which contains a set of commands used to set up a Docker image. These commands are the same commands one would normally execute manually in order to build the image.

The following command is used to build an image automatically using a Dockerfile:

```
$ docker build [OPTIONS IMAGE DOCKERFILE] .
```

Upon requesting to build an image, Docker automatically reads the Dockerfile, executes the instructions successively, and returns the final image [6].

The Docker daemon executes the instructions one at a time and commits any results to an image where necessary before outputting the ID of the new image. Whenever possible, these intermediate images are re-used by Docker to speed-up the image building process (Indicated by: *Using cache*) [9].

Figure 3: Image is created from Dockerfile [10]

2.4 Docker Hub

Docker hub is a cloud-based service for building, distributing and sharing applications or service containers. It provides a public or private centralized repository for images.

The key features and functions of Docker Hub include:

- Image Repositories: Find, manage, push and pull images from community, official, and private image libraries.
- Automated Builds: Automatically create new images when changes are committed to a source GitHub or Bitbucket repository.
- Webhooks: A feature of Automated Builds, allows actions to be trigger after a successful push to a repository.
- Organizations: Create work groups to manage user access to image repositories [11].

One may create a private repository whereby Docker images can be shared across machines by tagging, pushing and pulling images using the following commands:

Tag Image: \$ sudo docker tag CURRENT-TAG NEW-TAG

Push Image: \$ sudo docker push IMAGE-TAG

Pull Image: \$ sudo docker pull IMAGE-TAG

2.5 Data Volumes

A data volume is a special directory situated in one or more containers which bypasses the Union File System. It is a free-floating filesystem which does not require a connection to any particular container. Data volumes are generally used for persistent or shared data as they provide the following feature:

- Volumes are initialized upon container creation. Moreover, if a container's base image contains data then it is copied into the new volume.
- Multiple containers can share and reuse the same data volume.
- A data volume can be changed directly.
- Data volumes are persistent, they are not deleted upon container deletion. Docker will never automatically delete volumes when they are no longer referenced by a container.

A data volume is added to a container using the `-v` flag, which may be used multiple times to mount multiple data volumes. The command is as follows:

```
$ docker run [OPTIONS] -v LOCAL-FOLDER:CONTAINER-FOLDER
```

This will create a new volume inside the container, at the location specified by `CONTAINER_FOLDER` with a copy of the contents found at `LOCAL_FOLDER`. One may search for the volume location using the following command:

```
$ docker inspect -f {{.Volumes}} CONTAINER     [12]
```

Data Volumes are useful in situations where docker instances are required to communicate by storing data on the filesystem. Several docker containers can mount the same volume at once using: `$ docker run --volumes-from.`

Due to the fact that volumes are isolated filesystems, they are often used by transient containers to store the state from computations [13].

2.6 Docker Containers Vs Virtual Machines

Docker containers and Virtual Machines both allow the division of a single powerful machine to be shared across many applications, each with its own individual specific configuration requirements, such that the applications do not interfere with one another [13]. Nowadays, Virtual Machines provide the most portable way to deploy software at the cost of a large amount of overhead [6].

A typical virtual machine consists of the application, the necessary binaries and libraries as well as an entire guest operating system with its own memory management installed with the associated overhead of virtual device drivers, thus requiring a lot of space [5]. Furthermore, it requires a hypervisor to act as the virtual machine manager to share a single hardware host amongst multiple operating systems. The hypervisor allocates the host's processor and resources as required by the guest operating systems such that they appear to have their own resources without disrupting one another [14]. This makes it possible to run multiple instances of one or more operating systems in parallel on a single machine whereby each guest Operating System runs as an individual entity from the host system [15].

On the contrary, a Docker container provides most of the isolation of Virtual Machines at a fraction of their computing cost. This is due to the fact that applications are run natively on the underlying Linux kernel such that they are segmented from one another and from the underlying operating system [6]. They have similar resource isolation and allocation benefits as virtual machines, however a different architectural approach is used, resulting in increased portability and efficiency. Docker containers include the application and all required dependencies, whilst sharing the kernel with other containers as they run in an isolated process in user-space on the host operating system [5].

Docker containers do not require a hypervisor as they are executed using the Docker engine. Due to this, they are smaller than Virtual Machines, faster on start-up, provide less isolation and are possibly more compatible as they share the host's kernel. Furthermore, performance of an application running inside a container is generally equal to or better than running the same application in a Virtual Machine [15]. Moreover, Docker containers are not bound to any specific infrastructure and may be run on any computer [5].

Figure 4:

A fully virtualized system is allocated its own set of resources, uses minimal sharing, provides more isolation and requires much more resources. LXC gives less isolation, is more lightweight and requires fewer resources, thus easily allowing thousands of containers to run on a single host. Moreover a fully virtualized system commonly requires several minutes to start, whereas LXC containers take seconds [15].

2.7 Advantages

- Docker containers are lightweight and fast, greatly reducing the cycle time of development, testing and deployment.
- Docker does not require a hypervisor allowing a higher density of containers to be run on the host thus catering for larger workloads.
- Docker containers can run on almost any machine.
- Filesystem changes are managed through a set of layers which may be snapshotted, rolled-back, etc., allowing for change control at the file system level.
- Docker's lightweight containers greatly facilitate scaling up and down, as more containers can be launched when required, and can as easily be shut down when they are no longer needed.
- Docker images are designed in such a way that they may be ported across infrastructures making them suitable building blocks for hybrid cloud scenarios.
- Docker allows fast delivery of applications.
- Docker provides a way to set up local development environments which are just like live servers.
- The same operating system kernel is shared amongst containers running on a single machine allowing them use the RAM more efficiently and to start instantly.
- Docker images are built from layered filesystems in order to be able to share common files. This results in more efficient disk usage and image downloads [5].

3 R

3.1 Overview

R is a system for graphical techniques to create several types of data presentations, and for statistical computations including: linear and generalized linear models, non-linear regression models, classical parametric and non-parametric tests, clustering, etc... It consists of a language as well as a run-time environment with a debugger, graphics, access to system functions, and the ability to run programs stored in script files.

R is an interpreted computer language that allows branching, looping and modular programming using functions [17]. It is a combination of the S programming language and lexical scoping semantics. Most of the standard functions used in R are written in R itself, making it easier for users to follow. In addition, C, C++ and Fortran code may be linked and called at run time for computationally intensive tasks [18].

The R language provides objects, operators and functions which facilitate the process of exploring, modelling, and visualizing data. It is for this reason that R is commonly used by data miners and statisticians for performing data analysis and developing statistical software [19]. Moreover, it makes it possible to easily produce well-designed publication-quality plots including mathematical symbols and formulae where required.

It is a GNU project similar to the S language and is highly extensible through user-submitted packages for specific functions or specific areas of study. Furthermore, it has stronger object-oriented programming facilities than most statistical computing languages [20].

3.2 R + Docker = Rocker

Rocker is a project for running R using Docker containers. It provides a collection of Dockerfiles and pre-built Docker images that can be used and extended for many purposes.

For this project, a Volume is added to the Rocker container so that it will have access to the algorithm and the data upon which algorithm needs to be run.

Rocker is used by calling the algorithm script on container start up, and passing any parameters if necessary. The command is as follows:

```
$ docker run [OPTIONS] IMAGE -v LOCAL-FOLDER:CONTAINER-FOLDER  
Rscript SCRIPT-PATH [PARAMETERS]
```

This will create a volume inside the container, start up the container and run the specified script which should be found in the volume attached. Once the script executes, whether it terminates with an error or successfully, the container exits immediately.

4 Jupyter

4.1 Overview

Jupyter started off as IPython, an interactive Python shell. Nowadays it has grown into a powerful set of intertwined tools which maximize developer productivity in various languages, whilst working interactively [21].

4.2 Jupyter Notebook

The Jupyter Notebook is a web application for scientific computing and interactive data science. It provides an environment for users to write documents that combine live-code with narrative text, equations, figures, images, videos, links and visualizations [22]. Notebook documents are both human-readable documents containing the analysis description and the results, as well as executable documents which can be run to perform data analytics [23]. These documents encode a complete and reproducible record of a computation which can easily be shared with others on GitHub, Dropbox and the Jupyter Notebook Viewer.

The following projects allow for programmatically converting and manipulating notebook documents.

- [nbconvert](#): convert notebooks to static formats such as HTML, Markdown, LaTeX/PDF and reStructuredText.
- [nbformat](#): work with notebook documents programmatically [22].

4.3 Jupyter Kernel

A notebook kernel is a “computational engine” which is able to execute code contained in a Jupyter Notebook [32]. Kernels are separate processes that sit behind the Jupyter user interfaces and run code in a particular programming language [31]. Amongst several kernels, one kernel is the IR kernel which executes R code [32].

When opening a Jupyter Notebook, the associated kernel is automatically launched, and upon execution, the kernel performs the required computations and produces the results [23].

4.4 Advantages

- In-browser editing for writing code, with automatic syntax highlighting, indentation, and tab completion/introspection.
- The ability to compile and execute code from the browser, with the results of computations attached to the code which generated them.
- Provides a way to display computation results using rich media representations, such as HTML, LaTeX, PNG, SVG, etc.
- Allows for code commenting through in-browser editing using the Markdown markup language which is not limited to plain text.

- Allows users to easily introduce mathematical notation within markdown cells using LaTeX, and rendered natively by MathJax.
- Facilitates the sharing of code, data and results amongst other users [24].

5 Data Analytics in CERN Control System

5.1 Overview

The CERN control System is made up of a number of layers, namely:

1. Physical Layer - This layer contains several sensors which are used to detect the current temperature in the LHC tunnels.
2. Control Layer - This consists of various Programmable Logic Controllers (PLC) and Front-End Computers (FEC) which gather the data from the sensors.
3. Scada Layer - This system is a made up of distributed nodes which monitor the rest of the systems.
4. Data Analytics Layer - This layer performs algorithms on the data in search for information which would enable the users to better understand it. It also involves making the results visually available to the users.

Figure 5: CERN Control System Layers

5.2 Data Analytics Algorithm in R

The temperature of the electromagnets in the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) must be kept low to decrease resistance and allow for superconductivity, therefore sensors are used to monitor the temperature. The data gathered from these sensors is passed onto the control systems which are responsible for regulating the temperature through the use of valves. As the temperature increases and decreases the valves are opened and closed respectively.

The temperature constantly oscillates, causing the valves to oscillate with it by opening and closing frequently. If the valve begins to oscillate too frequently it may cause damage, therefore an oscillation detection algorithm, written in R, is used to detect such anomalies in the oscillations. While detecting frequent oscillations, the algorithm must also be able to ignore any sudden changes in the signal, such as random spikes in the temperature caused by system faults, electromagnetic field, etc. or if the user simply closed the valve manually.

It works by applying a number of filters to the signal as follows:

Figure 6: Oscillation Detection algorithm

All signals which make it through the above filters are considered to be anomalies.

5.3 Algorithm Parallelization

At present around 3000+ signals are analysed each day and this is expected to increase. Applying this algorithm on such a large number of signals is too much for a single machine to compute therefore the algorithm is run on the cluster which was set up in this project.

Each node in the cluster will have access to the data analytics algorithm to be run and will be assigned a subset of the signals to be analysed. The job of each node would be to apply the algorithm on this subset of signals in search for any anomalies.

6 Implementation

6.1 Overview

The idea behind this project is that the user will create a notebook on Jupyter in R and be able to run it in parallel. The Jupyter front-end allows for the users to write and compile code as well as view their data and results. The Docker back-end is one way of providing a scalable solution to running the algorithm in parallel with the aim of decreasing the time required for execution.

6.2 Implementation Details

A cluster of nodes on Openstack (See Appendix) was used throughout the implementation. The cluster consists of 6 nodes whereby 1 node acts as the master and the remaining 5 as the slaves.

Three Docker images were set up on the master:

1. Master image - The purpose of this image is to divide the task to be executed across the slave nodes, therefore it is only used by the master node. It contains the script for distributing the jobs and all the requirements for running this script. The script requires two arguments; the name of the file containing the algorithm and the path to the folder containing the data. These parameters must be passed to the container upon starting it.
2. Jupyter image - This image is assigned a port to host Jupyter. The container is run indefinitely on the master node, providing an environment for the users to write, compile and share code as well as to view and share their data and results.
3. Slave image (Rocker) - The only requirement of this image is that it supports R as it will be used as the environment to run the Data Analytics scripts in R on the slaves.

As soon as the user runs her/his R notebook, the job distribution process is as follows:

1. The slave image is pushed before-hand from the master onto the cluster's local Docker repository such that it is accessible for the slave nodes to pull.

2. Once the image is local on the nodes which are going to be used, the master sends commands to start up the required containers such that they begin running on their respective nodes.
3. A thread on the master is assigned to each container to keep track of its state.
4. Once a container finishes executing, it automatically exits and as soon as all the containers exit, the master container will also exit.
5. The results may also be viewed using the Jupyter container.

Figure 7: Underlying architecture displaying the relationship between the Docker containers and the other components.

The only pre-requisite for each node is that Docker is installed so that the containers may be run.

7 Evaluation

7.1 Results

The Oscillation Detection algorithm was run using a different number of nodes and containers each time and this is a table showing the time taken for each case:

Time in hh:mm:ss

	Number of Nodes						
		1	2	3	4	5	6 (1 Master)
Number of Docker Containers per Node	1	50:12:10	35:22:18	24:40:05	16:10:51	11:41:09	9:13:18
	2	39:14:05	17:13:09	15:26:05	12:32:28	10:34:16	7:11:56
	4	24:55:13	09:40:15	06:30:15	04:21:13	03:35:24	02:48:56
	8	15:24:10	06:25:16	05:44:30	04:08:21	03:15:20	02:32:13
	16	12:09:38	06:10:35	05:15:47	04:13:21	03:09:36	02:15:20
	32	09:08:02	05:30:21	04:38:02	03:25:20	02:11:33	02:01:14

The results in the previous table are plotted in the graph below:

We can see that as the system scales up and utilises more resources, the execution time greatly decreases. The time required for execution has significantly decreased by 96% from using the least resources (1 node and 1 container) to using the most resources (6 Nodes and 32 containers)

The above results show that adding a node to the system performs better than starting up a new container as the decrease in execution time is greater. This is evident when comparing, 1 Node 2 Containers and 2 Nodes 1 Container, 1 Node 4 Containers and 4 Nodes 1 Container and 2 Nodes 2 Containers, etc...

7.2 Scalability

The speed up is calculated using the following equation:

$$Speedup(n) = \frac{\text{execution time on 1 node}}{\text{execution time on } n \text{ node}}$$

Below is a graph showing the speed-up against the number of nodes used:

The scalability graph indicates that the largest speedup occurs when 4 containers are used. With 8 containers the speed-up is constant after 3 nodes. When 16 containers or 32 containers are used, the speed up begins to decrease after 5 nodes whereas with 2 containers or 4 containers the speed up increases after 5 nodes.

8 Conclusions and Future work

As seen in the Evaluation chapter, this project does indeed greatly decrease the time required to run Data Analytics algorithms on a large number of signals. The time required to perform analytics is far less than it was originally.

Future work would include the following:

1. Combine the two containers running on the master such that the master container starts up as soon as the user runs the script in the Jupyter container. At present the Jupyter UI can be used to write, compile and share code, however it runs the script locally. The command to execute the script through the master container must be manually run on the master.
2. Find an alternative to the Network File System (NFS) as at present the other nodes can only access the data through the master. This creates a bottleneck making the system more I/O intensive. A solution to this could be to use an Andrew File System (AFS) or a Distributed File System (DFS) similar to Hadoop DFS.
3. Make use of a job scheduler to add fault tolerance, such as re-running any jobs which may have failed or assigning fewer tasks to slow nodes and more to faster ones or even allocating jobs according to the time required until completion.

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Appendix: OpenStack

OpenStack is a free and open-source cloud operating system software that controls large pools of compute, storage, and networking resources throughout a datacentre. It is managed through a dashboard or via the OpenStack API, giving administrators control while empowering their users to provision resources through a web interface. OpenStack is ideal for heterogeneous infrastructure as it works with popular enterprise and open source technologies. Hundreds of the world’s largest brands rely on OpenStack to run their businesses every day, reducing costs and helping them move faster [25, 26, 27]. The goals of the OpenStack initiative are to support interoperability between cloud services and allow businesses to build Amazon-like cloud services in their own data centers [28].

OpenStack is a set of software tools for building and managing cloud computing platforms for public and private clouds. It allows users to deploy virtual machines and other instances which handle different tasks for managing a cloud environment on the fly. It makes horizontal scaling easy, which means that tasks which benefit from running concurrently can easily serve more or less users on the fly by just spinning up more instances. For example, a mobile application which needs to communicate with a remote server might be able to divide the work of communicating with each user across many different instances, all communicating with one another but scaling quickly and easily as the application gains more users [29].

Figure 8: Openstack Cloud Operating System [26]